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БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ
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KHOTAMOVA Madina Anvarovna
ODILJONOVA Mukhimaoy Savlatovna
Samarkand State Medical University**EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE PREVENTION AND TREATMENT
OF PERIODONTITIS AND THE ORGANIZATION OF DENTAL MEASURES FOR
WORKERS OF METAL PROCESSING ENTERPRISES**

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 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15008368>**ABSTRACT**

Prevention of periodontal diseases is a complex task, the solution of which requires conditions of both local and general nature, including social issues and problems of modern man.

Key words: periodontium, periodontal diseases, somatic diseases, dental plaque, dental plaque, prevention, oral hygiene

XOTAMOVA Madina Anvarovna
ODILJONOVA Muqimaoy Savlatovna
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti**METALLNI QAYTA ISHLASH KORXONALARI ISHCHILARI UCHUN
PARODONTITNING OLDINI OLISH VA DAVOLASH SAMARADORLIGINI
BAHOLASH****ANNOTATSIYA**

Parodont kasalliklarning oldini olish murakkab vazifa bo'lib, uni hal qilish uchun mahalliy va umumiy xarakterdagi sharoitlarini va muammolarini yechimi topish, ularni o'rganish va profilaktika choralari hamda zamonaviy davolash usullarini ishlab chiqishdan iborat.

Kalit so'zlar: periodont, periodontal kasalliklar, somatik kasalliklar, tish plastinkasi, profilaktika, og'iz bo'shlig'i gigienasi

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Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет**ОЦЕНКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ПРОФИЛАКТИКИ И ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ПАРОДОНТИТА И
ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ МЕРОПРИЯТИЙ ДЛЯ РАБОТНИКОВ
МЕТАЛЛООБРАБАТЫВАЮЩИХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ**

АННОТАЦИЯ

Профилактика заболеваний пародонта - сложная задача, решение которой требует условий как местного, так и общего характера, включая социальные вопросы и проблемы современного человека.

Ключевые слова: пародонт, заболевания пародонта, соматические заболевания, зубной налет, зубной налет на зубах, профилактика, гигиена полости рта.

Relevance.

In the process of intensive industrial development, the study of the role of harmful and health-related factors of the production environment is timely and very important. After all, unfavorable working conditions contribute to the formation of various pathological processes in the human body[1].

For practitioners, there is a question of choosing an adequate complex therapy for chronic generalized periodontitis in all. Given that bone resorption processes prevail in osteoporosis, certain features should be assumed when planning treatment of chronic generalized periodontitis in such cases.

One of the probable etiological factors is the low bone mineral density of the facial skeleton during postmenopause.

Currently, there is practically no substantiated information on the use of medications that correct mineral metabolism in the complex treatment of periodontitis, in particular, there is insufficient data on the effect of antiresorptive drugs on osteogenesis of the alveolar bone.

Periodontal diseases are one of the most common inflammatory and destructive diseases, which has been recorded in 4 billion people worldwide [8]. Along with this, the attendance of patients to dental clinics with periodontal diseases has increased, which represents 65% of all visits to the dental office [9].

The formation and development of inflammatory and destructive lesions of periodontal tissues is associated not only with local, but also with general factors. According to a number of surveys, periodontal tissue diseases are detected in 81% of menopausal women, in addition, periodontitis is the most common among these diseases of various forms

The long-term influence of a complex of production factors simultaneously with the deterioration of the health of workers, as a rule, can lead to pathological changes in the oral mucosa, periodontal diseases, and hard dental tissues [3].

Metallurgical production belongs to the industry with the most severe, dangerous and harmful working conditions, which have a direct impact on the functional systems of the body, change homeostasis, neuro-humoral regulation in it and lead to pathological changes in the oral cavity [5].

Harmful conditions for the production of metal structures, despite the availability of occupational safety and health measures, represent extreme conditions for workers and require further development of comprehensive programs for the prevention of major dental diseases.

The purpose of the study: to optimize rational measures for the prevention and treatment of periodontal diseases in workers of metal processing production (metal structures).

Research objectives:

1. To determine the prevalence and intensity of dental caries, the condition of periodontal tissues, oral hygiene of employees of the metal processing enterprise AZIA METAL PROF LLC and its branches in Kattakurgan and Urgut.

2. To study the state of functional parameters and nonspecific reactivity of the oral cavity, biophysical properties of mixed saliva in workers of the studied industries.

3. To study the psychophysiological parameters of the body depending on the intensity of the influencing factor in workers of metal processing enterprises.

4. To develop a set of sanitary and hygienic, general health and dental therapeutic and preventive measures aimed at improving the condition of periodontal disease in workers of metal processing enterprises.

The object of the investigation: it is planned to inspect the oral cavity of 120 workers of the main workshops of the metal processing enterprise AZIA METAL PROF LLC and its branches in Kattakurgan and Urgut. As a control group, the oral cavity of 35 employees of the studied enterprises who are not in contact with harmful factors of this production will be examined.

Research methods: clinical and instrumental, laboratory, biochemical, statistical.

Supposed scientific novelty:

The state of the structural and functional parameters of the oral cavity, some biochemical parameters of saliva in workers of the AZIA METAL PROF LLC enterprise and its branches in Kattakurgan and Urgut will be studied.

The complex of therapeutic and preventive measures aimed at improving the condition of periodontal tissues in workers of metal processing enterprises will be improved.

Practical significance of the research: The obtained clinical and experimental data will allow us to develop and put into practice an improved set of measures aimed at improving working conditions, preventing professionally caused diseases of the oral cavity, improving the organization of planning dental care for workers of metal processing enterprises.

The results of the work will be implemented in practical healthcare through the development and publication of methodological recommendations and information materials approved by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Individual oral hygiene as a method of preventing periodontal diseases should be given special attention. It is known that the main etiopathogenetic factor of inflammatory periodontal diseases are pathogenic and opportunistic microorganisms of dental plaque capable of forming biofilms. They can also support and provoke further development of many chronic general somatic diseases, and the risk of occurrence, development and further progression of both inflammatory processes in the oral cavity and general somatic diseases directly correlates with the degree of microbial contamination of the oral cavity. That is why dentists attach great importance to the quality of hygienic procedures performed by the patient and the individual selection of personal oral hygiene products, their effectiveness and safety. Modern therapeutic and prophylactic oral hygiene products (toothpastes, rinses, balms, gum gels) with proper selection and complex use are capable of providing a pronounced anti-plaque, antiseptic, anti-inflammatory effect, reducing gum bleeding due to the active components included in their composition.

In severe periodontal diseases, hygienic measures alone are no longer enough; they must be combined with complex treatment: conservative, surgical and orthopedic. However, without high-quality oral hygiene, any therapeutic measures and manipulations will be ineffective.

Conclusions. We draw attention to an important aspect: in order to succeed in the prevention of periodontal diseases, dentists must learn to talk with their patients, otherwise all medical measures and manipulations will be useless as long as we only treat, fill, and operate. The process of preventing any disease primarily consists of a person's awareness of its necessity, and until doctors learn to work on a mental level, all preventive measures will be reduced to columns of numbers in reports of medical and social institutions and departments, insurance companies.

In this regard, the goal of any prevention program should be an individual, i.e. a person with his illnesses, everyday and professional problems, character and characteristics of nutrition and other factors that influence the features of developing a personalized program. But all these measures will be effective only if each of us realizes that his life, health and longevity depend on how he treats himself and the world around him. To do this, a person must love himself, value his body and take care of it.

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